

**ENHANCING THE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM INDUSTRY' S ACTIVE COLLABORATION
WITH SCHOOLS TO MANAGE EMPLOYEE TURNOVER RATE**

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Abstract

This research empirically investigates collaboration between the Hospitality and Tourism industry and schools in career orientation delivery for 1st-year students that manage to survive under the COVID-19 pandemic. This study applied the thematic analysis method to analyse qualitative data from a set of texts, such as this study's interview transcript. The findings also explore the benefits to stakeholders, including career orientation and talent attraction management, personnel staffing in the Hospitality and Tourism industry, career orientation and students' perceptions and expectations for their future occupations, career orientation, and lecturers' perception of self-study development. This research fills the literature gap among the above relationships and points out the benefits in the Hospitality and Tourism industry and school collaborations to overcome difficulties during the COVID-19 epidemic in Vietnam.

Keywords: COVID-19, Vietnam Hospitality and Tourism, Career Orientation, Self-development, Career Perceptions and Expectations, Talent Attraction Management

Introduction

Before the pandemic, International Tourism growth at well-known destinations has increased other sectors' development, including education. However, it has led to the skilled labour shortage, lack of experienced teaching staff, and an unfitting curriculum (Nguyen & Chaisawat, 2011). Further, it is more challenging to recruit the right people for the right jobs and attract talents than ever for employers (Chapman et al., 2005). It seems like the war of attracting and retaining talent is never-ending (Guthridge et al., 2008). Talent management is the survival and essential issue in the Hospitality and Tourism Industry (Deery & Jago, 2015). Although a large body of research has discussed retaining and managing talents in the hospitality and tourism sector for employees, employers (Allen, Bryant, & Vardaman, 2018; Ashton & Morton, 2005; D'Annunzio-Green, 2008). However, talent attraction through education activities has not been concerned appropriately. There is some research on students' career orientation (Hodgkinson, Innes, & Hodgkinson, 2001; Zhou, Smith, & Spinelli, 1999) and some research on designing a suitable tourism curriculum (Lewis, 2009; Tribe, 2001; Tribe, 2009). However, there is less connection between Career Orientation and curriculum design for first-year students instead of mentioning graduates who performed a specific internship during the first year of their occupations, suggesting a smoother transition to the employment market (Margaryan et al., 2020). A careful consideration among career orientation and its relationship affecting stakeholders is lacking (e.g., Career Orientation and Talent Attraction Management in Hospitality and Tourism industry. Career Orientation affects students' perceptions and expectations for the future career; career Orientation role in teaching at Hospitality and Tourism school for 1st-year students).

A similar situation of recruiting the right people for the right jobs and attracting talents also occurred to respond to crises and their impact on hospitality and tourism industry employment. Thereby, we could also see fluidity, uncertainty magnify and exacerbate the industry's precarious nature from ongoing change during the COVID-19 epidemic (Baum et al., 2020). The Vietnam

Hospitality and Tourism industry has no income and has to pay for staff salaries and facility fees, which pushes the operation cost very high, causing some hotels to shut down and lay off people temporarily; some hotels are on sale and leaseback (Bui Thu, 2020). The beginning outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in Vietnam was on January 23rd, 2020, and the second is on September 17th, 2020. During this period, the hospitality and tourism industry is almost jumpy. After the first pandemic wave, it is in the recovery period; then, the second wave has knocked it down yet again. Accordingly, thousands of people working in the hospitality and tourism industry fall into unemployment (VnExpress, 2020a). Whereas before the epidemic, Vietnam was honoured with prestigious prizes like "Asia's Best Destination," "The world's leading heritage destination in 2019," and Vietnam is on the list of countries with the highest workforce in the travel and tourism industry worldwide in 2019 (Statista.com, 2020). Nevertheless, the accommodation and catering services were most heavily impacted during the pandemic, with significantly 740,000 jobs affected. (VnExpress, 2020b). However, the hospitality and tourism majors are still among the industries attracting many students to enrol in Vietnam (T.D.V, 2020). Under this situation, this paper aims to determine:

- How do the Vietnamese hospitality and tourism industry, schools, students, and faculties deal with the Career Orientation to respond to crises they face under COVID-19?
- What are the benefits that Career Orientation delivery collaborations bring to stakeholders during COVID-19? (to industry, students, faculties)
- Would the the1st-year students in hospitality and tourism majors worry about their future occupations during the pandemic?
- Is career orientation compulsory in the curriculum due to the hospitality and tourism industry being fluidity and uncertain?

In this study, the researchers explored research data based on the stakeholders' experiences among industry representative (human resource managers, department directors), students, faculties in the delivery of "Career orientation (CO)" in the academic year 2018 – 2019 students (first-year students) at hospitality and tourism schools in Vietnam before and during COVID-19. This research undertook a qualitative analysis to identify similarities and differences in stakeholders' experiences. It also provides a theoretical framework that could find better evidence to answer the research questions above.

Literature Review

The study will review the literature regarding Career Orientation and its benefits to stakeholders to understand why Career orientation could help stakeholders survive during the pandemic.

1. Hospitality and Tourism Industry and Schools Collaborations

There have been many career-oriented activities for students between the hospitality and tourism industry and schools, such as internships, field trips, training programs, or job fairs. A tourism internship could help students clarify their career intentions and explicit attitudes to their future professionals (Busby, 2003).

Some students expect that internship is their probationary period (Beggs et al., 2018). Others thought the tourism agency should provide orientation and training programs for interns, professional development opportunities, and full-time jobs after the internship (Beggs, 2008). Internships create opportunities for students to acquire practical skills, workplace experience,

improve students' professional value, develop personal maturity, and learn from their life experiences (Busby & Gibson, 2010).

Students could better understand the knowledge in class during field trips (Goh & Ritchie, 2011). A field trip is also a study trip to help students with interdisciplinary understanding through participatory learning experience; therefore, students can understand and orient better for their future careers (Zhang & Xiong, 2017).

For the training programme, the collaboration between industry professionals and lecturers in delivering some subjects in the tourism curriculum will help clarify vague knowledge that learners may be unsure to understand (Cooper & Shepherd, 1997). Cuffy, Tribe, & Airey (2012) stated that it is necessary to develop a lifelong approach in tourism education and training to develop student readiness.

Employers could promote their available positions in job fairs to target students of different positions in an organization (Milman & Whitney, 2014). Hospitality and tourism students choose careers by influences employers' branding; Employers must build a solid reputation, provide remuneration policies transparently or refer the current employees to share their experiences to attract potential candidates (Lin et al., 2018).

However, the above career-oriented activities are almost designed for final year students but not yet considered a subject to help first-year students choose the proper specifications and future careers. A hospitality and tourism curriculum should include a future career orientation subject to guide students and build their future with positive thoughts and breakthrough developments. (Ring et al., 2009).

2. Career Orientation and Students' Perceptions and Expectations of Future Occupations

Career orientation affects the career development of young students (Wood et al., 1985) who are growing up in a digital world with their career-oriented (Black, 2010). Career orientation affects students' GPA at different academy periods (McKenzie & Schweitzer, 2001). This paper will collect data from first-year degree students born in 2000, the last generation of Y (Eisner, 2005), also referred to as the internet. The sharpness, intellectual or technical ability, and know-how to apply technology in real life are tremendous advantages of the Y generation. Especially in the digital age, their flexibility and acumen will be further promoted (Black, 2010). The reason to choose this generation to research because they have had a whole year to communicate with hospitality and tourism industry representatives and faculties in Career Orientation activities while experiencing the COVID-19 pandemic. Thereby, they had time to consider whether their choices for this industry are proper.

Gen Y's hospitality and tourism industry's perceptions are low pay and long and unusual hours with fixed schedules (Richardson & Thomas, 2012). At the same time, Generation Y prefers to do an exciting job that can earn money and spend more time outside the office or work-life balance and autonomy at work (Szamosi, 2006). Y generation lacks an attachment to organizations and frequently switches jobs within their industry (Ayres, 2006).

Martin (2005), who calls this generation Y-ers, describes the main characteristics of Y Generation towards their careers as follows: "they are responsible for their work, seek flexibility and new experience, they are not interested in the lifelong job and frequently change careers several times during their working life. Y-ers respect managers who empower staff and are honest with

employees. They seek equality in the workplace, reasonable wages, and training opportunities (Morton, 2002). In general, Generation Y has high expectations of employers in salary policy, working environment conditions, promotion opportunities, and technology advancement (Oliver, 2013).

Gen Y students could need career advice and orientation right from the first - year to choose the right major for future occupations with such characteristics, perceptions, and expectations of works. However, very few studies have mentioned career orientation as a necessary subject for first-year degree students and its benefits while we usually hear about orientation in companies or high school training programs in Vietnam. In contrast, Employers will inevitably need to adjust to the new reality of having five generations of staffers working together and understand future staff desire, perception, and expectation are necessary (Meister, 2020).

3. A Connected Curriculum

A curriculum is connected if it shows a multidimensional relationship among academics, students, and the real world (Fung, 2018). The connection can be no less than twelve dimensions of connectedness (Please see table 1).

Table 1: A Connected Curriculum for Higher Education

A Connected Curriculum for Higher Education	
1	Between disciplines;
2	Between the academy and the wider world;
3	Between research and teaching;
4	Between theory and practice;
5	Between the student and teacher/lecturer/professor;
6	Between the student in her/his interior being – and in his/her being in the wider world;
7	Between the student and other students;
8	Between the student and her/his disciplines – that is, being authentically and intimately connected epistemologically and ontologically;
9	Between the various components of the curriculum;
10	Between the student's own multiple understandings of and perspectives on the world;
11	Between different areas – or components – of the complex organization that constitutes the university;
12	Between different aspects of the wider society. Especially those associated with society's learning processes.”

Note. (Fung, 2018)

Twelve dimensions of connectedness are detail discussed in some pieces of research. The benefits of listening to student voices in curriculum adjustments brought to school some tangible benefits such as the average score improved, the pass rate was maintained afterward, and improved interaction between students and teachers relating to curriculum development (Brooman et al., 2015).

A curriculum is called cohesion in hospitality and tourism when it raises and addressed social issues for stakeholders. For example, to design a curriculum better, social employment issues should be mentioned as objective measurements (Tribe, 2001). The society trend in hospitality and tourism is sustainable development, a hospitality and tourism curriculum concept, affecting students' perceptions (G. Busby, 2009). Globalization affects the hospitality and tourism economy

and education. The hospitality and tourism schools should meet globalization requirements in curriculum designing for learners with five steps: mission, aims, objectives, skills, knowledge, knowledge and skill matrix, course development, evaluation techniques (Smith & Cooper, 2000).

The COVID-19 impacts on tourism entrepreneurs create further stresses on tourism education. Apart from the virtualization of online delivery and learning processes, tourism students and graduates have to discuss their industry internships, future career paths. Tourism education is now facing changing its curriculum, reduce students' admissions, lack government sponsorship, and research funding (Sigala, 2020). The following section explores the questions presented above about career orientation and stakeholders' benefits during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology

The researchers divided two periods before and during the second wave COVID-19 to conduct lengthy, semi-structured interviews with industries' representatives, students, and lecturers to understand how career orientation can support stakeholders during the pandemic. We conducted data collection from March 2020 to Sep 2020, the researchers applied the traditional face-to-face and online interviews, and each interview lasted about 30–45 minutes.

The interviewees will have time to get familiar with the topic in advance. Each interview was recorded and transcribed. Recording interviews allow researchers to focus on the content of interviews and then ask questions or clarify where it is essential to avoid distraction during interviews due to researchers' notetaking ((Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). Data analysis is a process of two steps: “The first step dealt with single interview transcripts; the second step is a content analysis process of themes from the research questions (Please see table 2).

Table 2: Sample Interview Questions for stakeholders

Sample Interview Questions FOR STAKEHOLDERS	
Groups	Questions
Industry	1. How have you responded to this challenging period in the career orientation application? 2. What have you done for your personnel staffing with 1st-year students?
	1. What are the benefits achieved when applying career orientation to cope with obstacles?
Lecturers	(1) What are the benefits of delivering career orientation for first-year students during this challenging period? (2) What do you want to accomplish better?
Students	(1) What is your perception of a future career during the pandemic? (2) What is your most desirable company?

1. Participants

This study explored the stakeholders' experiences in the mutual collaboration of delivery career orientation for the academic year 2018 to 2019 for first-year students at hospitality and tourism schools in Vietnam. Hays (1982) suggested 10 – 30 participants or Belle (2008) suggested that 12 participants are enough for interviews.

However, this research will conduct qualitative research via interviews with no predetermined number of participants. The interviews will be stopped when the collected interview data is saturated, which means no new information or themes appear in the interview. The saturation progress usually occurred within the first twelve interviews, and essential elements for meta themes were performed as early as six interviews (Guest et al., 2006).

2. Data collection and analysis

Qualitative techniques allow researchers to constitute and analyze qualitative databases. There are some techniques such as analysis of interview transcripts (Burnatd, 1991), photographs (MacKay & Couldwell, 2004), multimedia (Viken, 2006), or internet websites (Davidson & Yu, 2008). This research includes open-ended questions to explain the phenomenon under study, and the data comes from interview transcripts. Focus group interviews were chosen to collect data due to their benefits on the rich source of information (McLafferty, 2004).

The interviewer number was over 56 people from industry representatives, faculties, and students who have the same background and collaborated in joint career-oriented cooperation programs. However, during the interview, the data collection was saturated at 14 students, 10 Industry professionals, and 12 lecturers. All interviewees were categorized to their occupation titles as 12 lecturers (LR) are LR1- LR12; 14 students (ST) are ST1 - ST14; 10 Industry professionals (PR) are PR1 - PR10 (Please see table 3)

Table 3: Demographic profile of interviewees for qualitative interview

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Interviewee categories	Title	Interviewee features	No of interviewee
PR 1 - PR 10	Industry professionals	Travel agency	10
LR 1 - LR 12	Lecturer	Travel and tourism school	12
ST 1 - ST 14	Students	Travel and tourism school	14

The researchers used the Thematic analysis method to analyse qualitative data, which is usually utilized in a set of texts, e.g., interview transcripts, to identify, analyse, and interpret patterns of meaning or "themes" within qualitative data. Three-step applied to conduct the thematic analysis in this study, including "Familiarization," is the first step by getting a thorough overview of all the data collected, reading through the text, and taking initial notes before analysing individual items. The second step is "Coding," which means highlighting text sections, usually phrases, or sentences, and coming up with stenography labels or "codes" to describe their content. The third step is "Generating themes" by looking over the codes created, identifying patterns among them, and coming up with themes. The fourth step is "Reviewing themes," which is needed to ensure all themes are valuable and accurate representations of the data. If the researcher encounters themes, they could be split up, combined, discarded, or created new ones: whatever makes them more valuable and accurate (Braun & Clarke, 2012) (please see table 4).

Table 4: Results of thematic analysis

Results of thematic analysis		
Stakeholders Main themes	Coding	Coding transcript
Industry		
Personnel Staffing	Employment-based adjustment (flexible)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The way of thinking about hiring experienced personnel has changed. We also have the responsibility to train potential personnel we are seeking for future hiring, and 1st-year students are the potential ones that we would like to train for future recruitment after the pandemic ended. • We work with the school to share experiences, support hospitality, and travel skill training and nurture talent for the post-COVID-19 period. • We assigned 1st-year students to practice their skills alternately at our company. We both have low-season employees on duty while reducing our payroll and insurance costs. • The hotel business is in a challenging period. Some key personnel also think of switching positions and apply to other firms. Working with schools in CO will create opportunities to interact with a young and passionate team. We assist schools in training at the site to help 1st-students improve their skills. They can become part-time employees. Key personnel who join in this collaboration can have additional income from schools. Such collaboration will help firms to reduce the operating costs, retain key staff during the epidemic season. • We have closed our hotel temporarily. Some employees themselves also want to quit their jobs. We need to find a new potential team that does not need to work right now but may be available when needed.
	Ensuring Readiness in recruitment and staffing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have worked with several prestigious hospitality and tourism schools on the job training to facilitate future recruitment and staffing. • We have students' personal and contact information records. • We work with faculties to better understand student ethics and character.
	Simple HR Management system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple HR Management system. • The young and dynamic team brings a fresh atmosphere to the hotel during the offseason.

	Operational costs reduced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We always have school access to active, enthusiastic personnel sources, which are available in large quantities. • Minimizes operating costs during the epidemic. • Instead of paying labour costs every month, we now deal with casual, part-time wages or only shift meals to cope with the difficulties. Besides, there are certain risks because the youth team will not be mature enough to handle every challenging situation during the season.
Talent Attraction Management	Grab and Retain Quality Talent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "We showed our desire to attract some talent students; we prepared a talent recruitment plan and have counteroffer ready (e.g., about some policy to attract talent students)" • "We delivered in class and treated our candidates as customers." • "We keep up the communication on social media and market ourselves as friends."
	Earn the trust of students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "We offered our trust first, then listened effectively and asked what is most important to students' job expectation, job turnover, their birthday, keep connections, and learn how to improve potential candidate retention."
	Build stronger connections with students and improve communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students feel challenged and motivated in their future jobs." • "When they are closer to industry representatives, they are typically satisfied with their expectation and perception." • "Having a good relationship with firms' staff also provides positive motivation for students."
Self-development	Self-development during COVID-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "During the pandemic, hotels, travel agencies can improve their quality service, SOP, and infrastructure." • "We speed up and shorten construction time and are ready to open up to welcome guests as soon as the pandemic ended." • "We try to retain the key labour force and wait for the COVID-19 pandemic pass. By the way, we do open some short-term training courses to improve employee professional skills and encourage them to learn more foreign language proficiency with monthly allowance amounts."
Realistic of challenging labour market	Future occupations without a degree and proper specialization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "If someone is looking for a job at this time, it is not easy because the competition rate is high, and the hotels are almost closed." • "We worried that if the pandemic lasts, the skilled and professional personnel will find

		<p>other stable industries (even in times of crisis) to work (even us)."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once we have joined this program, we can have an amount of money coming in from school. • "We want to keep in contact and the talented students list for future recruitment." • "We are happy to get the talent list from schools during CO delivery. However, we are sorry to say that we cannot promise anything." • "We need to prepare the mental stability for students in the pandemic." • "A lack of a communicated plan for education and career orientation could lead to more students entering the labour market (without a degree or certificates)."
Students		
Career Perceptions and Expectations	Worry and confusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I do not know how long the coronavirus pandemic will last. If it still lasted until graduation, then I might not find a job". • "I am perplexed and need someone to talk about this." • "I am worrying too. However, if the pandemic would end, tourism will flourish again, at least the domestic market." • "I am confused that if the pandemic affects my future career job." • "I did not know if my specification choice is right." • "During this crisis, I wonder when tourism will recover." • "I need some talk shows from school, teachers." • "I love to work in tourism and hospitality, but I do not see the light for this job shortly." • "I am thinking about changing other majors."
	Career planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Tour operators, hotel coordinators are the better choice than a tour guide." • "I have already noted some skills that are required to reach that position." • "I am preparing my CV to send to the HR department; they would like me to join them as part-time staff." • "I have some potential listing of companies that I want to work with and their contacts." • "I suppose that I prefer sales & marketing to tour guides because I have good communication skills."
	Exploring strengths and weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "During the process of CO learning, HRM & Department Director asked me about my strengths and weaknesses, it was a difficult

		<p>question, and I do not know what my personality strengths and weaknesses are.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “After learning about human personality, I was happy to know that my personality type is expressive, its strength is good at communication and enthusiastic, but its weakness is talking too much. Sales & Marketing is a suitable job for this type of personality”. • “I might be an HR coordinator in the future because my personality type is gracious; I will always be patient and diplomatic.”
	Right major	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I think the epidemic is only a temporary dilemma. After that, tourism will recover, at least domestic tourism.” • “I feel worried too, but I trust in my chosen major, and I want to become a sales and marketing coordinator.” • “I will work as a receptionist in a hotel because a tour guide is a hard-working job.” • “I think that the hotel coordinator is more suitable for me.”
Self-development	Connect them to professionals and advisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I like my advisor; she is kind and closed with us.” • “The HR manager treated us so well; he is frank and shared with us his personal information, and we can contact him on social media.” • “I am not confident in communication, but now I feel much better because of the sincerity of advisor and industry representatives.” • “We are bolder in asking questions because we know we will get their sincere answers.”
	Utilizing the available opportunities to learn and communicate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I met enthusiastic staff who dedicated and answered my questions.” • “I asked them about their position, they introduced it and instructed us to prepare the appropriate knowledge for that position (All students)” • “I have the opportunity to meet experienced tour guides.”
	Understand how to employ relevant skills and knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I have learned how to organize in the classroom or teambuilding.” • “I studied with a positive attitude because I found myself quite fit with this career.” • “I learned to communicate through the ways that managers communicated with us.” • We should work in a team to train our speaking skills, problem-solving.” • “We should work independently on writing about decision making.”

	Know the job market requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I need to take time to test my English skill certificate because it is essential to apply for the international license for a tour guide.” • “The labour market requests Korea and Chinese guides.” • “I should study Korea to work as an international tour guide for Korean visitors.”
Faculties		
	Changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “We have to update suitable knowledge to meet with what students need during the pandemic.” • “CO course aim is to help students with future career orientations. Therefore, we need to steer students’ original choices clear. Besides, it is possible to suggest other alternative jobs for students if the pandemic situation still poses the greatest threat in the coming years.” • “Lecturers need to update official news from the government and indicate students’ directions during the epidemic.” • “Hospitality studying does not mean working in a restaurant, hotel, or travel agency. All fields are required to learn and be aware of the word “hospitality.” Therefore, they could know and have flexible applications while for their future careers.” • “I realized that the teaching situation is different in this duration. I sometimes feel like I am an emotional robot which is smart enough to detect all issues” (smile) • “I receive many questions regarding students’ future careers and try to indicate them appropriately.” • “I have learned from students in different situations and tried to find the best solutions for them.”
Self-development	Updating practical knowledge and Self-study training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I want to arrange my time to renew the specification knowledge from the industry. However, I have spent most of the time in the session deliveries at school.” • “I should plan for the industrial activities to test my knowledge in the summer holidays.” • “I think that CO encourages any lecturer to experience lifelong teaching and learning from the real world.”
	Promote program to the broader world, benefits to school enrolment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a good impression for first-year students is the best word of mouth marketing for school recruitment. • Some students have shared admission information on their social networks like Facebook, Zalo, and Instagram.

	Improve teaching quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is a subject that is combining theory and practice from industry. Thus, we can learn more from industry representatives and fill in the gaps in our knowledge. • Students are excited about attending class with industry representatives.
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Note. Analysis by author, 2020

An unstructured interview usually highlights an in-depth understanding, and it allowed working within interpretive research and maximum flexibility to explore themes and obtain rich data (Auditors, 2011). Interviewees were advised to be flexible and did not need to follow the order of questions, but they need to share their views according to the questions' contents.

Findings

With the thematic analysis, as mentioned in the methodology, this article's findings indicate that hospitality and tourism firms, students, and schools are mixed symbiosis with mutually beneficial relationships from the stakeholders' perspective. We can perceive this connection through two theoretical models Fig 1 and Fig 2 below.

1. Hospitality and Tourism industry and School Collaborations

According to the industry perspective, the management of tourism personnel under COVID-19 is no longer hiring experienced people but about flexible recruitment, minimizing and simplifying the personnel operation system. Join-in-hand with hospitality and tourism schools in education and training is a must. It would be challenging if a person were looking for a job due to the high competition rate, and the hotels are almost closed. Besides, if the pandemic lasts, the skilled and professional personnel would quit this career to find others, much more stable ones. Faced with this situation, firms choose the solution to join hands with the school to train the younger and ambitious 1st-year students for future recruitment because they were unsure about the pandemic situation and the tourism recovery in the future so that preparation for available team to recruit shortly is a must. Firms also confirmed that they could not have enough budget to recruit experienced staff due to high salaries or train newcomers. For example, some industry representatives stated that: *"We work with the school to share experiences, support hospitality, and travel skill training, and nurture talent for the post-COVID-19 period. We assigned 1st-year students to practice their skills alternately at our company. We both have low-season employees on duty while reducing our payroll and insurance costs."* Some worried about future qualification recruitment due to: *"a lack of a communicated plan for education and career orientation could lead to more students entering the labour market (without a degree or certificates)."*

Besides that, the employees who joined the collaboration can have incomes that could support their lives through a difficult time. In schools where industry exposure is a longer extension, students and industry representatives will know each other better, the level of active interaction will increase rather than depending on the one side of schools. For example, some students said they know clearly about the human resource staff that they can contact together for any questions: *"The human resource manager treated us so well; he is frank and shared with us his personal information, and we can contact on social media."* Thus, in this challenging period, human resource management in the hospitality and tourism industry keywords are **"flexible"** and **"training and nurturing."**

2. Career Orientation and Student Perception and Expectation of Future Occupations

From the hospitality and tourism students' perspective, some students have concerned about the unpredictable pandemic situation. They need someone to address what they should do. Some are worried about their future career if the epidemic remains until graduation. Several students wish to change to other study fields. However, most interviewed students with positive thinking argue that the tourism industry will recover soon, at least domestic tourism. Hence, among their perceptions, the hospitality and tourism personnel management keyword is "**positive thinking**."

In faculties' opinions, career orientation supports students steering clear and keeping the choices they originally made for their future careers. Besides, faculties should learn what students worry about or suggest alternative jobs if the pandemic is still severe and complicated in the coming years. Also, faculty members should continually update official news and equip themselves with the knowledge to assist students as soon as possible. Accompanying students with mental issues during this challenging period is the lecturers' duty. Therefore, among their views, the hospitality and tourism personnel management's keyword is "**right direction**" from schools (please see figure 1).

Figure 1

Proposed theoretical framework – Understanding stakeholder's response to the challenging COVID-19 period

Note. From data collection and designed by the author

The collaboration between the hospitality and tourism industry and schools in giving the right direction and nurturing talents will create more dynamic and confident students with more positive thoughts on their chosen career path.

3. A connected curriculum

Besides the above activities, some hospitality and tourism organizations have taken this time to speed up, shorten construction, and ready to re-open up for guests welcome as soon as the pandemic over. For example, "*they persist and do some short-term training courses to improve employee professional skills and learn more foreign language proficiency.*" (PR3.5.8.10)

Nevertheless, not all hospitality and tourism organizations can do that. Training a young, healthy, skilled, ready team is necessary for recruiting or replacing activities. The participation between

industry and schools in delivering career orientation is such an opportunity. Some industry representatives commented: *"We would like to keep in contact with the talented student list for future recruitment; We are happy to get the talent list from school during career orientation delivery. However, we are sorry to say that we cannot promise anything"; "During the pandemic, students' mental stability is important for themselves and future hospitality and tourism business"* (PR2.3.5.6.10.11)

Students are confused when they enter online classes because they are worried about future careers and may make unwise decisions at various times. Some human resource managers stated that *"A lack of communicated plans among stakeholders in delivery career orientation could lead to more students entering the labour market (without a degree or certificates)."* (LR3,4,9,10)

4. Career Orientation and its Benefits to Stakeholders

- Career Orientation subject is necessary and beneficial from the industry's viewpoint:

Career Orientation subject supports hotel and travel agencies in grabbing and retaining quality talents. Collaboration with hospitality and tourism schools can save expenses in sourcing and training new human resources. Some interviewees shared that:

"We desire to attract some talent students, we prepared a talent recruitment plan and have counteroffer ready (e.g., about some policy to attract students in talent list" (PR1,4,5,7).

"We deliver in class and treat our candidates like customers" (PR10,7,8,3).

"We keep up the communication on social media and market ourselves as friends" (All PRs).

During one year of interacting with students, the industry representatives have their talent lists that work and promote them as brand ambassadors.

Career orientation subject delivery is an opportunity for hospitality and tourism organizations to build relationships with students and potential markets in class and on sites. Besides, available teams for recruitment in the future when needed is necessary. To get students' trust, some employers offer respect to students such as *"we offered our sincere first then listened effectively and asked what is most important to students' job expectation, job turnover, their birthday, keep a connection and learn how to improve potential candidate retention"* (All PRs).

Career orientation delivery is an opportunity for building stronger connections with students and improve communication. Some interviewees shared that *"students feel challenged and motivated by their future jobs when they know us clearly"* (PR7,4,9). *"When they are closer with us, they are typically satisfied with their expectation and perception"* (PR1,4,5,6,7,8). *"Having a good relationship with us also provides positive motivation for students"* (PR2.3.6,10).

Career Orientation is an opportunity for industry representatives to learn labour market needs and improve their human resource management policy accordingly (All PRs).

Career Orientation is essential and beneficial for industry and talent attraction activities, which are challenging in human resource management from the industry's viewpoints.

- Career Orientation is Necessary and Beneficial from the Students' Viewpoint

Career orientation affects students' perceptions and expectations of career planning and the decision-making process in implementing career choice. It provides the right direction to their life in achieving long-term career goals and career objectives. It helps students make the right decision in their study choice, what jobs to do, and explore their interests. Some interviewees mentioned:

"Tour operator, hotel coordinators are the better choice than tour guide" (ST12,14,7,2,15).

"I have already noted some skills that are required to reach that position" (ST3,4,5).

"I am preparing my CV to send to the HR department, they would like me to join them as a part-time staff" (ST5,11,13,) or "I have some potential list of companies that I want to work with and their contacts" (ST1,4,6,8,10,12) or "I think I prefer sales & marketing to tour guides because I have good communication skill" (ST7,5,1,4).

Career Orientation helps students explore their strengths and weaknesses, identify their skills and interests. Some interviewees expressed:

"During the process of CO learning, HRM & Department Director asked me about my strengths and weaknesses; It was a difficult question because I am not sure about my personality, strengths, and weaknesses." (ST3,7,8,4,9,13,1,12).

"After learning more about personality type, I am happy to know that I am expressive. Its strength is good at communication and enthusiasm. However, spending too much time talking is the weakness that sales & marketing could be suitable with" (ST4, 5)

Other interviewees felt that *" They were born to be an HR coordinator because their personality type is amiable. They will always be patient and diplomatic" (ST6,14).*

When students realize their personalities, it is also essential to help them choose the right job. Career orientation directs students to choose the right majors and future occupations under experienced mentors' supports.

For example, two interviewees expressed that *"I feel that hotel coordinator is more suitable for me than travel & tourism majors" (ST2,15) or "Female interviewees felt tremendous pressure with tour guide job because the market is lacking labour and they have to work very hard" (ST1,14,13).*

Some interviewees would like to switch to other fields such as *"I have thought that a tour guide is the one could travel everywhere, but after studying career orientation, I realized that It is not the suitable one for me, I think I need to discuss with my parents about switching other faculties." (ST7).*

Career orientation tied stakeholders together in a mutually reinforcing relationship with their reputation closely interdependent with each other. Students built their good relations with industry representatives, lecturers, and confidence in communication for one year. Some interviewees shared:

"I like my advisor; she is kind and close with us" (ST2,14,15,9)

"The HR manager treated us so well, he is frank and shares us his contact and connect us on social media" (ST11,5,3,7):

"I am not confident in communicating with others, but there was warmth in advisors and industry representatives' greeting and their handshakes that make me optimistic." (ST6,4);

" They will almost always be willing to answer our questions even though we keep asking questions from time to time." (ST12,13,4,6,8).

Career Orientation helps students utilize opportunities to make field trips and observations at sites. *"I met enthusiastic staff who dedicated me and answered my questions" (ST4,11,6).*

"I make some questions of their job positions, they shared and instructed how we can prepare for these positions" (All students).

"I have the opportunity to meet experienced tour guides" (ST13,12,1,4,6).

Career Orientation teaches students how to employ jobs' skills and knowledge, such as attitude, communication, teamwork, self-management, problem-solving, and decision-making. Some interviewees shared:

"I have learned how to organize in the classroom or a teambuilding" (ST,8,9).

"I studied with a positive attitude because I found myself quite fit with this position" (ST10,1,4,3). "I learned to communicate through the ways that managers communicate with us" (ST9,5,14,13). "We should work in a team to train our speaking skills, problem-solving" (ST11).

"We should work independently on writing about decision making" (ST13,10).

Career orientation subject helps students to acquire the job market requirements. Some interviewees discussed that:

"We learned about the job market which is a shortage for tour guide" (ST3,5,4,8);

"The labour market requests tour guides who can speak Korean and Chinese " (ST13,9);

"I should study Korean to work as an international tour guide" (ST1,15);

"I need to take time to test English skill because it is essential to apply for the international license" (ST14,6,10)

Career orientation helps some students think about switching to other majors. Some interviewees said that:

"I have registered to switch to hospitality majors for the next semester" (ST15).

"I may choose to study hospitality because the tour guide is a hard-working type" (ST2)

"I think that the hotel coordinator position is for me" (ST7).

These findings show that career orientation is essential and beneficial for first-year students in all situations.

- Career Orientation is necessary and beneficial from the hospitality and tourism school's viewpoints.

Career orientation delivery is an opportunity to update practical knowledge and self-study training to faculties. Career orientation supports them in interacting better with students and industry and update useful knowledge. Some shared that *"I want to arrange my time to renew the practical knowledge from the industry. However, I have spent most of the time in the session deliveries at school"*; (LR1,2,3,5,6,7,8,9,12,14,15)

"I should plan for the industrial activities to test my knowledge in the summer holidays" (LR1,2,3,5,6,7,8,9,12,14,15)

"I think that career orientation encourages any lecturer to experience lifelong teaching and learning from the real world " (LR2,5,6).

Career Orientation encourages hospitality and tourism schools to promote their program to a broader world, which relates to lecturers' interaction with first-year students to create positive first impressions and thinking. Some interviewees told us that *"Creating a good impression for 1st-year students is the best word of mouth marketing in school enrolment activities"* (LR6,14,1). *"Some students have shared admission information on their social networks like Facebook, Zalo, and Instagram"* (LR2,5,9,11).

Some lecturers shared that *"Career Orientation is necessary for 1st-year students in the curriculum. It brings benefits that the program developers have not thought of before. In the process of working with hospitality and tourism organizations, we found the gap in our knowledge, which was needed to implement a change accordingly to improve teaching quality"* (LR12,9,8,7,3,5). *"Besides, when students interact with hospitality and tourism organizations for one year, they will hold the opportunities to receive internships for the last year without going through an interview"* (LR1,2,3,4,5,6,11).

Some lectures shared that "*The subject is combining theory and application from industry*"; "*Students are excited attending class with industry representatives*" (LR6,3,1,7).

These comments highlight that CO helped lecturers in self-development, and it is an excellent opportunity to attract new enrolments and market the school brand name.

The findings highlight the viewpoints of three stakeholders involved in stakeholders' collaboration in career orientation delivery. Most beneficiaries are the hospitality and tourism industry, students. Surprisingly, there are some commonalities in their viewpoints. For example, all stakeholders appreciate Career Orientation as an opportunity for them to develop and implement their potential plans.

Discussion and Conclusion

This paper's theoretical implications provide three significant categories of necessary and beneficial career orientation, as Figure 2 illustrates (Please see figure 2). Trommsdorff (1983) introduced the career orientation theory, and Nurmi (1993), who contributed to the concept of positive career orientation in the future and showed that it is associated with a series of positive results in young people. This study contributes to the body of the literature in three primary ways as follows.

1. Career Orientation and student perception and expectation of future occupations

- Career orientation is a necessity for first-year students' perceptions and expectations. Students should learn more about employment opportunities before starting their learning program to minimize the gap between expectations and perception (Kusluvan & Kusluvan, 2000).
- Career orientation affects and changes the first-year students' awareness of the hospitality and tourism career and helps students make the right choice. Students usually choose the university depending on the university-related factors and the student-related ones (Petruzzellis & Romanazzi, 2010).
- Students can also plan a career path to motivate themselves towards a better future throughout their academic years. (Pratten & O'Leary, 2007)
- Students could explore their characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses within career orientation learning. Besides, career orientation brings students communication opportunities with faculty and industry representatives from face-to-face to social networks. Therefore, students can take advantage of these opportunities to develop their professional communication skills better.
- The number of students is saturated at 14, which is higher than in other research.

2. Hospitality and Tourism industry and schools collaboration

- **To Industry**
 - ✓ Career orientation supports the industry in sourcing and managing talents. Organizations should identify and invest in outstanding candidates (Berger & Berger, 2011). Students have their own unique, which need to be identified and helped to release them.
 - ✓ Career orientation collaboration is an opportunity for organizations to grab and retain quality talents from schools. Besides, the interaction with students offers a process for defining employment policy problems that any organization could be facing (E. Martin, 2011).

- ✓ During interaction and communication in career orientation delivery, the industry can earn trust and build stronger connections with students through social networks, one of the most critical internal marketing (Wong et al., 2017).
- **To School**
 - ✓ Career orientation helps schools and lecturers in self-development. During CO activities, hospitality and tourism lecturers can improve their teaching quality. The university should ensure education quality accreditation by designing curriculum and outcomes assessment with the current education growth (Massy, 1997).
 - ✓ Lecturers will have opportunities to renew valuable knowledge and self-study during career orientation interaction. The mutual collaboration among stakeholders could promote learning programs, build prestigious brands, and market reputation to the broader world. The university's reputation influences students' decision to enroll (Russell, 2005).
 - ✓ Career orientation should be compulsory for the first-year students in the curriculum at school. However, we found that very rare Vietnamese universities consider career orientation a subject within the curriculum during the interview.

3. A connected Curriculum

Career orientation has studied in several previous as a determinant in choosing careers (Suutari, 2003), or career orientation in women's career choices (Betz & Fitzgerald, 1987) or career orientation of men in non-traditional occupations (Simpson, 2005) or the development of a protean career orientation (Sargent & Domberger, 2007). However, they have not considered it compulsory to connect the hospitality and tourism industry, students, and schools for a long-term relationship. Suppose the universities rearrange the curriculum with career orientation as a compulsory subject so the engagement between the industry and school will be permanent than activities. Under a subject for 1st-year students, the industry can be active in relationships with students without dependence on school connecting in field trips, job fairs, or short training courses. The relationships could help them not to be passive dependent on the schools. Interaction and engagement will be longer in the following academic years and lead to flexible, proactive hiring. Students are also more active in the job search process, and the schools are also less strenuous in organizing job fairs over the continual years.

The research paper seeks to fill the literature gap by examining how industry, students, and schools deal with career orientation to overcome obstacles during the epidemic. Hospitality and tourism schools in Vietnam should add career orientation into the curriculum as compulsory due to its benefits.

Limitation and Future Research

This research contributes to an empirical and practical approach in collaboration among stakeholders to deal with difficulties during COVID-19 in Vietnam. Students do not have enough information on the labour market; lecturers lack practical experience, valuable knowledge of students' future careers, and industry challenges in personnel staffing during the pandemic. The research approach still has some limitations, such as the sample of industry professionals within hospitality and tourism collected in the center of cities where hospitality and tourism business are rapidly developing and affected quickly by COVID-19. Other researchers can collect data outside the city center for future research or choose broader representatives and conduct quantitative surveys to recognize the differentiates among groups when the pandemic is over.

Figure 2

The proposed theoretical framework of necessary and beneficial CO to stakeholders

Note: From author’s collected data and design research frameworks

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